

The Bounds for the First Zagreb Index and the Forgotten Topological Index of a Graph

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Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. The first Zagreb index and the forgotten topological index of a graph G are defined respectively as $\sum_{u \in V} d^2(u)$ and $\sum_{u \in V} d^3(u)$, where $d(u)$ is the degree of vertex u in G . In this note, we present an upper bound for the first Zagreb index and a lower bound for the forgotten topological index of a graph with minimum degree at least one.

Keywords : The first Zagreb index, the forgotten topological index

Mathematics Subject Classification : 05C09

1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges, the degree of a vertex v is denoted by $d_G(v)$. We use δ and Δ to denote the minimum degree and maximum degree of G , respectively. A set of vertices in a graph G is

independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . For disjoint vertex subsets X and Y of $V(G)$, we use $E(X, Y)$ to denote the set of all the edges in $E(G)$ such that one end vertex of each edge is in X and another end vertex of the edge is in Y . Namely, $E(X, Y) := \{e : e = xy \in E, x \in X, y \in Y\}$.

The first Zagreb index and the forgotten topological index of a graph were introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić [5] and Furtula and Gutman [4], respectively. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index, denoted $Z_1(G)$, and its forgotten topological index, denoted $F(G)$, are defined as $\sum_{u \in V(G)} d_G^2(u)$ and $\sum_{u \in V(G)} d_G^3(u)$, respectively. Using one inequality in [3], we in this note present an upper bound for the first Zagreb index and a lower bound for the forgotten topological index of a graph with minimum degree at least one.

Theorem 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges such that $\delta \geq 1$. Then

[1]

$$Z_1(G) \leq \frac{\beta\Delta^3 + e}{2} + (n - \beta)\Delta^2$$

with equality if and only if G is a union of $\frac{n}{2}$ independent edges.

[2]

$$F(G) \geq 2\beta\delta^2 - e + (n - \beta)\delta^3$$

with equality if and only if G is a union of $\frac{n}{2}$ independent edges.

2 A Lemma

We use Theorem 2.14 on Page 8 in [3] as our lemma.

Lemma 1 [3]. If a_k and b_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, s$) are real numbers and c_k and d_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, s$) are nonnegative real numbers, then

$$\sum_{i=1}^s d_i \sum_{i=1}^s c_i a_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^s c_i \sum_{i=1}^s d_i b_i^2 \geq 2 \sum_{i=1}^s c_i a_i \sum_{i=1}^s d_i b_i.$$

If c_k and d_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, s$) are positive real numbers, the equality holds in the above inequality if and only if $a_k = b_k = K$, where $k = 1, 2, \dots, s$ and K is a constant.

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges such that $\delta \geq 1$. Clearly, $1 \leq \beta < n$. Let $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Then

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = |E(I, V - I)| \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Since $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) + \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v) = 2e$, we have that

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) \leq e \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Applying Lemma 1 with $s = \beta$, $a_i = c_i = d(u_i) \geq \delta \geq 1$ and $b_i = d_i = 1$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, \beta$, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^3(u_i) \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d(u_i) \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} 1^3 \geq 2 \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^2(u_i) \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} 1^2 = 2\beta \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^2(u_i).$$

Thus

$$\beta \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^3(u_i) + \beta e \geq \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^3(u_i) \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d(u_i) \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} 1^3 \geq 2\beta \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^2(u_i).$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^3(u_i) + e \geq 2 \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^2(u_i) = 2 \sum_{u \in I} d^2(u).$$

[1] Hence

$$\begin{aligned} Z_1(G) &= \sum_{w \in V} d^2(w) = \sum_{u \in I} d^2(u) + \sum_{v \in V - I} d^2(v) \\ &\leq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^3(u_i) + e}{2} + (n - \beta)\Delta^2 \\ &\leq \frac{\beta\Delta^3 + e}{2} + (n - \beta)\Delta^2. \end{aligned}$$

If

$$Z_1(G) = \frac{\beta\Delta^3 + e}{2} + (n - \beta)\Delta^2,$$

then, from the above proofs, we have that $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e$ which implies that $\sum_{v \in V-I} d(v) = e$ and thereby G is a bipartite graph with partition sets of I and $V - I$. Furthermore, we have that $d(u) = \Delta$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in I$. Thus $\Delta|I| = |E(I, V - I)| = (n - |I|)\Delta$. Therefore $|I| = |V - I| = \frac{n}{2}$. From Lemma 1, we have $d(u_i) = 1$ for each i with $1 \leq i \leq \beta$. Hence G is a union of $\frac{n}{2}$ independent edges.

If G is a union of $\frac{n}{2}$ independent edges, a simple computation can verify that

$$Z_1(G) = \frac{\beta\Delta^3 + e}{2} + (n - \beta)\Delta^2.$$

[2]. From

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^3(u_i) + e \geq 2 \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} d^2(u_i) = 2 \sum_{u \in I} d^2(u),$$

we have

$$\sum_{u \in I} d^3(u) \geq 2 \sum_{u \in I} d^2(u) - e.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} F(G) &= \sum_{w \in V} d^3(w) = \sum_{u \in I} d^3(u) + \sum_{v \in V-I} d^3(v) \\ &\geq 2 \sum_{u \in I} d^2(u) - e + (n - \beta)\delta^3 \geq 2\beta\delta^2 - e + (n - \beta)\delta^3. \end{aligned}$$

If

$$F(G) = 2\beta\delta^2 - e + (n - \beta)\delta^3,$$

then, from the above proofs, we have that $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e$ which implies that $\sum_{v \in V-I} d(v) = e$ and thereby G is a bipartite graph with partition sets of I and $V - I$. Furthermore, we have that $d(u) = \delta$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \delta$ for each $v \in I$. Thus $\delta|I| = |E(I, V - I)| = (n - |I|)\delta$. Therefore $|I| = |V - I| = \frac{n}{2}$. From Lemma 1, we have $d(u_i) = 1$ for each i with $1 \leq i \leq \beta$. Hence G is a union of $\frac{n}{2}$ independent edges.

If G is a union of $\frac{n}{2}$ independent edges, a simple computation can verify that

$$F(G) = 2\beta\delta^2 - e + (n - \beta)\delta^3.$$

This completes the proofs of Theorem 1.

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